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IEA Wind TCP Task 43

**A guide to improving digital
organisational culture in wind energy**

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Executive Summary

This document presents a guide to strengthen digital organisational culture in wind energy, illustrated through a specific use case of a digital twin for wind farm asset health monitoring. This is important because digitalisation can accelerate wind energy deployment by improving efficiency, insights, and new services, yet organisational culture is a major barrier: factors such as openness to feedback, blameless learning, creativity, and innovation can shape whether data is shared, digital tools are tested, and AI and digital twins are successfully developed and adopted. The recent IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Questionnaire 2024 identified several weaknesses in fostering digital organisational culture across both teams and organisations. For example, a lack of an organisation-wide digitalisation strategy, insufficient funding and support for teams to experiment with innovative solutions, a fragmented organisational structure, a lack of digitalisation training, and a shortage of employees with digital and communication skills were identified as key barriers to digitalisation. As well as organisational culture, other barriers to digitalisation exist, which are being examined in other projects connected to IEA Wind Task 43.

These suggestions are split by the three stakeholder groups: central management, HR departments and team leaders. The suggestions for central management are to (1) create a centralised support hub with digitalisation expertise, decision-making capacity, and agile budget access to actively enable team-initiated digital ideas, (2) publish a clear, multi-year digitalisation roadmap with goals, owners and milestones, (3) make digital transformation a required goal in every business unit, (4) appoint a Chief Digital Officer and “digital ambassadors”, (5) flatten decision layers, and normalise constructive feedback and continuous learning, and (6) institutionalise experimentation and blameless learning at the organisational level. The suggestions for HR departments are to (1) provide digitalisation training, (2) recruit domain-aware digitalisation experts, (3) train leaders to champion digitalisation, (4) design hybrid learning formats that combine digital skills training with emotional readiness, and (5) create a “digitalisation maturity profile” per unit. The suggestions for team leaders are to (1) empower teams with true ownership for digital transformation, (2) make team success stories visible and integrate them into strategic communications and (3) apply proven team practices to improve leadership capability and cross-team decision-making. Upskilling of the three stakeholder groups may be required for effective implementation.

Following an introduction in Section 1, the suggestions with examples are presented in Section 2. The suggestions are summarised in Section 3.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document is intended to act as a guide to help central management, HR departments and team leaders contribute to improving digital organisational culture in wind energy.

1.2 Background information

Digitalisation is widely recognised as a key enabler for accelerating global wind energy deployment, through its potential to improve efficiency, create insights, and develop products and services. A recent study showed that organisational culture is one of the three main challenges to digitalisation in wind energy [1], and that aspects of organisational culture such as open feedback processes, positive handling of failures, creativity, and innovation can have a large impact on digitalisation. For example, they can affect how readily data is shared, how digital technologies are tried and tested, or how AI-based systems and digital twins are designed and used. At the same time, particular challenges in the wind energy sector such as extreme siloed attitudes could make implementing a digital organisational culture difficult. Then we use the term “Organisational culture”, we mean an organisation’s beliefs, values and attitudes, and how these influence the behaviour of its employees [2]. “Digital organisational culture” refers to aspects of organisational culture that specifically influence digitalisation, such as a culture of digital innovation and a transparent digital strategy [3].

The study that identified organisational culture as one of the three main challenges to digitalisation in wind energy also demonstrated that the level of experience and scientific knowledge on the topic was relatively low. Therefore, the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Questionnaire was run in 2024, aiming to understand the connection between organisational culture and digitalisation in the wind energy sector. The results were recently published [4], showing that teams, rather than whole organisations, are the stronger engines of digitalisation culture, and companies outperform universities and research and technology organisations. Organisation and team size were found to have little bearing on cultural readiness, and digital momentum rises bottom-up while large organisations lag in funding and tools. Large organisations were found to supply more formal training, small ones to give better support to unsure staff, and team culture was found to depend more on its leaders and members than on hierarchy or number of employees. Qualitative comments identified the main barriers to digitalisation to be a lack of resources, vague strategies, siloed structures, risk-averse leaders, and weak digital skills. Suggested solutions included earmarking time and money, creating explicit strategies, improving communication and leadership, rewarding innovation, and investing in targeted training or specialist hires. These results of the questionnaire analysis allowed a set of recommendations and implementations to be suggested, intended to help team leaders and relevant decision-makers in fostering digitalisation.

1.3 Summary of the contents

In this document, the recommendations and implementation suggestions from [4] are described in more detail and attributed to different stakeholder groups (central management, HR departments and team leaders). In order to enhance understanding, implementation suggestions are made for one use case, in which we imagine a team within an organisation to be developing and operating a digital twin for wind farm health monitoring (where applicable). This use case represents the use case “Asset health monitoring” from Table 1 in Section 3 of the IEA Wind Joint

Best Practices for the Classification and Valuation of Digital Twins in Wind Energy [in review] or from our separate list of use cases [5]. Upskilling of the three stakeholder groups may be required for effective implementation. The division between stakeholders and suggestions is not entirely strict, and stakeholders may overlap in some cases, depending on the organisation's structure.

1.4 Contributors

As well as the authors (Sarah Barber from the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland, Saleema Panda from the Atlantic Technological University, Sligo, Ireland and Jagadish Vallarampara from Teraom Limited, London, UKSciences), a number of other IEA Wind Task 43 participants and collaborators have contributed to this report. In particular, the reviews from Dirk Bendlin, Ramboll (Germany), Andy Clifton (Enerlace, Germany), Ali Khodam (Aalborg University, Denmark), Charles MacGill (NLR, USA), Christian Jonsson (KUDO Software, UK), and Anna Maria Sempreviva (DTU Wind, Denmark) were essential. Contributions from the members of the IEA Wind Task 43 Organising Committee Yu Ding (Georgia Tech), Stephen Holleran (Brightwind), Nikolay Dimitrov (DTU Wind) and Gibson Kersting (RWE) were key for setting and maintaining the overall strategic direction of the document.

1.5 Intended audience

The intended audience for this document include people from central management, HR departments and team leaders in the wind energy sector, as well as anyone interested in how to contribute to improving digital organisational culture in wind energy.

1.6 Intended benefit or usefulness of report

By taking the suggested steps, the stakeholders can define strategies for improving digital organisational culture in their organisation, thus fostering digitalisation. This can lead to improved digital innovation, and therefore cost savings and value creation in diverse areas of the organisation.

1.7 Special acknowledgments

Thanks to the co-authors of [4], Anna Maria Sempreviva, Jeffrey Clerc, and Anne Hegemann, who contributed to the idea for this document.

2. Main body of report

The following suggestions are tailored to three key stakeholder groups: central management, HR departments, and team leaders. These stakeholders were chosen based on the stakeholders addressed by the recommendations in Table 3 in [4], developed as a result of the analysis of the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey.

The three stakeholder groups were defined as follows:

- **Central management:** Sets the overall strategy for the organisation, balancing investment, risk, and performance across development, construction, and operations. They make key decisions on digitalisation, sustainability goals, and how projects contribute to wider corporate and climate objectives.
- **HR departments (with support from IT departments):** Responsible for attracting, developing, and retaining the workforce needed for safe and efficient wind energy operations, from technicians and engineers to data specialists. They shape organisational culture, skills development, diversity and inclusion, and change management around new technologies and ways of working. Support from IT departments is essential to ensure the required technical expertise.
- **Team leaders:** Manage day-to-day work in specific areas (e.g., O&M crews, control room staff, engineering teams), translating high-level strategy into concrete tasks and priorities. They play a critical role in safety, performance, communication, and in the actual adoption of new processes or digital tools on the ground.

The division between stakeholders and suggestions is not entirely strict, and stakeholders may overlap in some cases, depending on the organisation's structure.

2.1 Suggestions for central management

SM1. Publish a clear, multi-year digitalisation roadmap with goals, owners and milestones

Why this is important: A lack of organisation-wide digitalisation strategy was one of the key findings of the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey. A digitalisation roadmap addresses this gap by providing clarity, aligning priorities, and ensuring that digitalisation is embedded across business units rather than pursued in isolated pilots. It also signals commitment to long-term investment in skills, data platforms, and governance. Linking roadmap objectives to ESG frameworks and SDGs ensures that digitalisation supports climate resilience, resource efficiency, and inclusive innovation.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could form a cross-functional steering committee to develop a multi-year roadmap with regular Objectives and Key Results (OKRs), and to track open data compliance and publish roadmap progress regularly on the executive dashboard, including ESG- and SDG-linked KPIs. The roadmap could be based on the “IEA Wind Task 43 Technical Report - Evolving the Wind Energy Sector Towards Frictionless and Sustainable Data Usage” [8]. The roadmap should be communicated along with a clear message of the importance of digitalisation to the organisation. An implementation example for our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring” is shown in Figure 1. It is composed of five phases, each with 3-6 months iterative cycle. The scope of the roadmap is limited to a single wind farm but includes all relevant business units. This keeps the project technically manageable while broad enough to demonstrate that digitalisation can be effectively embedded across the company culture. Once the pilot wind farm is successful, the solution can be scaled and replicated across the rest of the wind turbine fleet. This helps the organisation to achieve a stronger culture of innovation and continuous learning. By following the roadmap and monitoring performance through OKRs, the organisation moves from digital experiments to a coordinated, scalable, strategic digitalisation effort, enabling faster and more effective Digital Twin deployment.

Figure 1. An example iterative digitalisation roadmap that could be created by a company with a business unit carrying out our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring” (DBP = Design Bases and Performance).

SM2. Make digital transformation a required goal in every business unit

Why this is important: The IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey showed that digitalisation is not often recognised as a core corporate objective. A lack of strategic prioritisation can lead to fragmented efforts, underinvestment, and missed opportunities for innovation and efficiency. Embedding digital transformation as a required goal ensures that it becomes a central driver of operational excellence, innovation, and sustainability.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could embed business unit digital goals in annual scorecards, benchmark business units against external peers, and align efforts with national and industry priorities, such as net-zero targets, sectoral digitalisation, and contributions to SDGs [6], guided by forward-looking roadmaps and robust data governance. This should be supported by clear metrics, feedback loops, and regular reviews to drive innovation, collaboration, and readiness for advanced technologies, including building policymaker skills and piloting new technologies through peer learning and case studies, backed by data essential to the ESG framework. Furthermore, the goals would be communicated along with a clear message of the importance of digitalisation to the organisation. Figure 2 illustrates how an organisation-wide digital transformation roadmap (see SM2) can be translated into actionable goals for individual business units, such as one carrying out our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring”. Clear metrics, regular reviews, and peer learning are mapped to operational elements, including early engagement, Transport and Installation (T&I), and Operations and Maintenance (O&M) for different stakeholder scenarios, such as bottom-fixed turbines, floating turbines with moorings, and jack-up installation vessels, and connected to Sustainable Development Goals (e.g., SDG 7, 9, 13, and 17) with ESG-backed data.

Figure 2: Digital Twin Roadmap linking metrics, feedback loops, peer learning, and ESG-backed SDG goals for SM3 implementation”

SM3. Create a centralised support hub with digitalisation expertise, decision-making capacity, and agile budget access to actively enable team-initiated digital ideas

Why this is important: One of the findings of the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey was that the budget for bottom-up digital initiatives is often limited, and processes for acquiring this funding tend to be slow. A centralised support hub can provide access to expertise and budget for team-initiated digital ideas. The dashboard should not only track funding but also visualise performance metrics such as downtime reduction, predictive accuracy, and carbon savings to demonstrate impact.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could (i) launch a small “Digital Sandbox” micro-grant scheme with rapid approval cycles, (ii) establish an “Innovation Helpdesk” that pre-screens project ideas, approves funding quickly, and proactively escalates barriers, and (iii) maintain a digital dashboard to track and communicate supported initiatives across the organisation. It should be ensured that the hub operates under clear governance with transparent criteria for funding decisions and publishes regular summaries of supported projects. An example of how a centralised support hub could be used for our digital twin use case, “Asset health monitoring”, is shown in Table 1. It shows different possible components of a support hub, each with a concrete implementation example, a summary of the possible impact and an ESG or SDG link for reference.

Table 1. Implementation example for SM1 for our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring”.

Support hub component	Concrete implementation example	Impact	ESG/SDG link for reference
Trainings	Provides training on modelling platforms such as MATLAB and ANSYS Twin Builder	Teams develop technical readiness to implement digital pilots	SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 9 (Industry Innovation)
Innovation Helpdesk	Provides technical support by granting access to SCADA datasets and necessary simulation/tool licenses	Ideas become proposal-ready	ESG Governance, SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure)
Digital Sandbox	Allows for testing a small pilot prototype digital twin predicting blade strain and turbine yaw misalignment using real-time SCADA data	A working prototype that shows value before investment	SDG 13 (Climate Action), ESG Environmental
Digital Dashboard	The pilot's progress is displayed on a real-time dashboard accessible across the organisation	Increased organisational transparency and shared learning	ESG Governance, SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption)
Internal seed funding	After successful prototype results, a larger investment is approved to deploy a digital twin to all turbines in the wind farm	The digital twin becomes an organisation-wide capability	Net Zero Alignment, SDG 7 (Affordable Clean Energy)
Feedback platform	The prototype successfully predicted strain patterns, but the real-time feed showed delays during high-frequency wind fluctuations. The team suggested improving data sampling rates and applying filtering to remove noise during gust conditions.	Encouraging bottom-up innovation	ESG Social (Knowledge Sharing), SDG 17 (Partnerships for Goals)

SM4. Appoint a Chief Digital Officer and “digital ambassadors”

Why this is important: Appointing a Chief Digital Officer (CDO) and digital ambassadors ensures strategic leadership, cultural alignment and improved communication about digital transformation across the organisation. It helps overcome fragmented efforts, resistance to change, and slow adoption of digital tools, barriers identified in the wind energy sector by the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey. A CDO provides executive-level accountability, cross-organisation communication while digital ambassadors foster bottom-up engagement and cross-team visibility. One of the key aspects of this role is to ensure a shared understanding of the importance of digitalisation within the organisation.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could establish a central Digital Office led by the CDO, supported by a project manager, enterprise architect, and data strategy and governance lead, as shown in Figure 3. The data strategy and governance lead role is responsible for establishing clear data ownership, maintaining data quality and metadata standards, ensuring alignment with FAIR principles, and coordinating data governance processes across business units. This role also supports analytics teams by ensuring that data is trustworthy, interoperable, and ready for AI-driven applications. In many organisations, this position combines responsibilities similar to those of a data steward, a data manager, and a data governance focal point. Cultural challenges should be identified upfront to guide change-management actions and ensure digitalisation is implemented effectively. Some of the activities of the Digital Office could be to (i) create a self-service data lake and collaboration portal to enable secure, transparent data sharing across business units, and to (ii) run cultural initiatives and innovation activities including digital innovation town-halls, fail-forward sessions, and idea challenges to promote experimentation and peer learning. A digital ambassadors network could involve rotating digital ambassadors across teams in order to cross-pollinate ideas and build digital literacy and a shared understanding of the importance of digitalisation within the organisation.

Figure 3: Example of an organisational structure of a Digital Office for SM4.

SM5. Flatten decision layers, and normalise constructive feedback and continuous learning

Why this is important: Flattening decision layers and normalising constructive feedback and continuous learning fosters agility, transparency, and innovation, which are key cultural traits for successful digital transformation. In the wind energy sector, hierarchical bottlenecks and risk-averse leadership were identified as barriers to digitalisation in the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey. A flatter structure empowers teams to act quickly, while a feedback-rich environment encourages experimentation and learning from failure. As wind farms expand into more dynamic and risk-prone environments, including offshore locations and larger, more complex turbines, lessons learned and risk mitigation become increasingly critical. Particularly for our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring”, organisations must foster a culture of agility and learning.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could start by (i) reducing approval layers for pilot projects to accelerate innovation cycles, and (ii) delivering multi-session executive digital-literacy programmes to equip leaders with the mindset and tools to champion transformation, (iii) hosting regular “fail-fast / learn-fast” review sessions to share insights and celebrate calculated risk-taking, and (iv) embedding feedback loops into team rituals such as retrospectives and peer reviews. An example of how decision layers could be flattened between the CEO, central management and CDO (see SM4) is shown in Figure 4. An example of how the CDO could be integrated into the rest of the organisation is shown later under RL1 in Figure 6.

Figure 4: Example of a flattened hierarchy, including a Digital Office, for SM5.

SM6. Institutionalise experimentation and blameless learning at the organisational level

Why this is important: Institutionalising experimentation and blameless learning fosters a culture of innovation, resilience, and continuous improvement, which is essential for navigating the complexity and uncertainty of digital transformation in the wind energy sector.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could start by (i) introducing “failure credits” that can be redeemed for future funding when lessons are transparently shared, (ii) adding the number of experiments run to organisational OKRs to visibly reward innovation efforts, (iii) running regular retrospectives across teams to reflect on outcomes, share insights, and (iv) normalising learning from failure by creating a safe space for experimentation, where calculated risks are encouraged and learning is prioritised over blame. An example of different failure credits for our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring” is shown in Table 2, inspired by [7]. Credits are given with different values, whereby more value is assigned to outcomes with more learning opportunities. This is done to avoid blame and encourage constructive response to so-called “failures”.

Table 2. Example of failure credits for our digital twin use case “Asset health monitoring”, inspired by [7].

Outcome	Example	Credit value
Maximum organisational learning; strengthens innovation culture	Digital solutions deployed on time and yield measurable operational improvements; Lessons fully captured, transparently shared	4
Reduces repeat mistakes	The Open Data Portal used as required, some insights or user experience improvements are derived; Lessons captured and shared	3
Partial improvement in processes	Initial attempts at cross-team planning fail, but lessons inform better meeting structures and role clarity; Some lessons captured	2
Minor learning	Projects fail to deliver solutions, and lessons are not documented; Little or no lessons captured	1

2.2 Suggestions for HR departments

SH1. Provide digitalisation training

Why this is important: HR departments are central to supporting organisational digital readiness. As the wind energy sector increasingly adopts digital technologies, such as AI, digital twins, and data-driven platforms, staff across all levels must be equipped with the skills and confidence to engage with these tools. The IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey identified weak digital skills and a lack of shared understanding as barriers to digitalisation. Without targeted training, organisations risk uneven adoption, resistance to change, and missed opportunities for innovation, efficiency, and safety. Structured digital training not only accelerates technology uptake but also supports workforce resilience and ESG compliance, ensuring alignment with global standards and regional development goals¹.

How it can be implemented: Organisations could start by (i) providing “Digital 101” onboarding for all new employees to establish a baseline understanding (a foundational training programme that introduces employees to essential digital concepts, tools, and practices, delivered through accessible formats and aligned with organisational goals, as well as discussing the importance and benefits of digitalisation), (ii) offering expert-led sessions and concise e-learning modules, tracked through the HR information system, (iii) hosting regular webinars open to all staff to promote continuous learning and cross-functional awareness, (iv) requiring basic digital certification for promotion to higher roles to embed digital competence into career progression, (v) creating mentoring programmes that pair technical leads with communications coaches to bridge skill gaps, and (vi) partnering with industry to offer secondments and guest lectures, especially for universities and research organisations, to expose staff to real-world digital applications. Table 3 gives an overview of the possible structure of “Digital 101” training.

Table 3. Overview of the possible structure of a “Digital 101” training course.

Main theme	Concrete examples (wind energy context)
1) Digital mindset & ways of working	Agile vs. waterfall basics; “iterate fast” with pilots; user stories; working in cross-functional teams; documentation habits, semantic alignment, the importance and advantages of digitalisation
2) Data fundamentals & “FAIR” basics	What is good data vs. bad data; metadata and naming conventions; types of data (assets, turbines, components); data quality checks; basic KPIs
3) Data governance, security & compliance	Data classification (public/internal/confidential); access management; phishing basics; secure sharing with vendors; privacy concepts; incident reporting
4) Digital tools stack & collaboration hygiene	Typical stack: ticketing (e.g., Jira/ServiceNow), docs/wiki, Teams/Slack etiquette, versioning (SharePoint/Git basics), dashboards (Power BI/Tableau)
5) Analytics & AI basics for wind energy	Descriptive vs. predictive analytics; anomaly detection for SCADA; condition monitoring examples (gearbox/bearing); forecasting (wind/power); how to interpret model outputs
6) Digital twins & asset lifecycle thinking	What a digital twin is; linking different data; change management and updating; typical use cases (performance, maintenance planning)

SH2. Recruit domain-aware digitalisation experts

Why this is important: Offshore wind operations involve complex, high-risk environments where digital tools like digital twins, AI-driven forecasting, and remote monitoring are essential. Recruiting digitalisation experts with domain knowledge ensures that digital solutions are tailored to the realities of offshore logistics, safety protocols, and environmental conditions. These experts can bridge the gap between operational teams and digital platforms, accelerating innovation and improving resilience.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could start by launching a targeted recruitment campaign led jointly by HR and the Chief Digital Officer (see SM4), focusing on candidates with experience in offshore wind operations and digitalisation. As summarised in Table 4, this could include outreach to marine engineering networks, partnerships with universities and research institutes for secondments and guest lectures, and tailored job descriptions that highlight the need for cross-disciplinary expertise in digitalisation, semantic alignment, data literacy and cybersecurity basics, and offshore domains within the offshore wind sector.

Table 4. Example of elements of a targeted recruitment campaign.

Recommendations for HR	Examples	CDO Support
Recruitment	Renewables Performance Engineer, Data Engineer, Wind Data Analyst, Digital Data Specialist	Defining digital roles, sourcing talent, guiding evaluation and onboarding.
Outreach	Internship programs, University Collaborations, Industry Associations	Access to Digital Tools and Data
Guest Lectures	Wind Asset Health Monitoring, Cybersecurity for Wind Digital Systems	Identifying digital skill gaps and arranging training/ mentorships

SH3. Train leaders to champion digitalisation

Why this is important: Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping organisational culture and driving digital transformation. In the wind energy sector, conservative mindsets and resistance to change were identified as key barriers in the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey. Training leaders to champion digitalisation helps overcome these challenges by fostering a culture of innovation, constructive feedback, and continuous learning, which is essential for scaling technologies like digital twins, AI, and data platforms in complex environments such as offshore wind.

How it could be implemented: The organisation could start by delivering a multi-session executive digital-literacy programme that focuses on the strategic aspects of digitalisation - why it matters, how it creates value, and how leaders can support and enable expert teams - while building appropriate awareness and strategic understanding of digital tools and trends in the industry, for example, in offshore wind operations. The training could include modules on Digitalisation, AI & Future Trends, and Data Management & Governance, framed around high-level impacts and decision-making considerations rather than technical details and tailored to the sector's unique challenges. Additionally, hosting regular "fail-fast / learn-fast" review sessions would help normalise experimentation and learning from failure, fostering a culture of innovation and resilience. In-house training and curated industry insights, such as those listed in Table 5 should be provided to deepen contextual understanding, while leaders should be encouraged to actively participate in cross-functional digital initiatives and innovation town-halls to promote collaboration and visibility. This approach gives leaders enough understanding to evaluate opportunities, set priorities, and remove barriers, leaving technical depth to the experts and supporting the development of confident, informed leaders capable of championing digital transformation across offshore wind organisations.

Table 5. Examples of different wind digitalisation leadership training that could be offered by HR.

Training for leaders	Impact	Example
Agile Mindset Development	Encourages early testing, iteration, and adoption of new technologies	The leader understands the potential value of tools like Digital Twin and asks expert teams to assess feasibility and suggest options to reduce downtime. Teams embrace new technologies or processes faster.
Leadership Communication Training: Effective Coaching and Feedback	Building trust and engagement promotes continuous feedback and growth	The leader encourages open dialogue. Teams feel safe raising concerns or suggesting improvements.
Strategic Innovation Programme	Encourages a culture of innovation, builds strategic thinking	Team leaders learn to identify and evaluate new technologies at a strategic level, then run small-scale pilots. Team members feel empowered to propose new ideas and solutions.

SH4. Design hybrid learning formats that combine digital skills training with emotional readiness

Why this is important: The findings of the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey showed that digital transformation in the wind energy sector requires not only technical competence but also emotional readiness and resilience. As organisations adopt advanced technologies like digital twins, AI, and IoT, employees must be equipped to navigate change, uncertainty, and evolving roles. Hybrid learning formats that combine digital skills with emotional readiness help build confidence, reduce resistance, and foster a culture of adaptability and psychological safety.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could start by offering courses such as the one listed in Table 6. These programmes could combine mandatory modules, covering tool literacy, cyber hygiene, and data awareness, with optional drop-in sessions such as "Digital Friday Clinics." At the team level, organisations could implement "Learning Circles" to encourage peer support and shared learning. In smaller entities, mutual mentoring between younger digital natives and senior professionals can bridge generational gaps and promote inclusive digital adoption.

Table 6. Examples of different Emotional Resilience Trainings for leaders organised by HR.

Emotional Resilience Training	Impact	Example
Emotional Intelligence for Future Leaders Training	Improves decision-making under uncertainty and prevents reactive behaviours.	Leaders stay composed and make informed choices when digital systems or predictive models produce unexpected results.
Mindfulness & Stress Management Training	Leaders can adapt to operational uncertainties, changing regulations, or new technologies.	During a severe storm, SCADA systems generated false alarms. The leader, trained in mindfulness, maintained focus, facilitated structured troubleshooting, and prevented panic-driven actions.
Psychological Safety in Transformation Training	Equips leaders to create a safe environment where teams can share ideas, learn from failures, innovate confidently, and accelerate digital transformation in wind energy operations.	A team is deploying a Digital Twin to monitor turbine health. The leader encourages the team to share failures, discuss uncertainties, and propose alternative approaches.

SH5. Create a “digitalisation maturity profile” per unit

Why this is important: Understanding the digital maturity of each unit within an organisation enables targeted interventions, resource allocation, and strategic planning. It helps identify strengths, barriers, and leverage points, ensuring that digital transformation efforts are context-aware and locally relevant. This approach supports continuous improvement and fosters a culture of transparency and accountability, shown by the IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey to be a key factor to successful digitalisation.

How it could be implemented: Organisations could develop a digitalisation maturity profile for each team, department, or site and make them visible on an interactive dashboard. The CDO could be responsible for this. They should include metrics such as digital tool adoption, data literacy levels, collaboration practices, and innovation engagement, and be updated regularly. Digital goals can be integrated into OKRs or target-setting systems that reflect specific local levers. In larger organisations, an annual "Digital Culture Ritual" could be institutionalised, featuring storytelling, a fail-forward night, and recognition of the boldest digital teams to celebrate progress and inspire others. The profiles could include aspects such as strategy alignment, technology adoption, skills and capabilities, culture and mindset, openness to experimentation, feedback, and cross-functional collaboration, and data management and governance. Each unit could self-assess or be evaluated through a structured framework, with scores or levels (e.g., Emerging, Developing, Mature, Leading). This would allow benchmarking across units and inform tailored support strategies. Dashboards could visualise progress and highlight areas needing attention, while periodic reviews would ensure the profiles remain dynamic and relevant. An example of a digital maturity profile for our digital twin use case is shown in Table 7.

In a wind energy organisation, achieving higher levels of digital maturity requires continuous adaptation to emerging digital technologies that support process automation and operational optimisation. This includes adopting advanced digital tools for data acquisition, analytics, and intelligent control systems across wind energy assets. It is important to have a digital mindset, which can be achieved by fostering a supportive organisational culture. This involves encouraging innovation, cross-functional collaboration, and openness to digital change at all operational and management levels. Also, to increase digital maturity, the organisation requires adequate allocation of resources, including investment in digital infrastructure, training programmes, and long-term digital transformation strategies. Strategic resource planning ensures that digital initiatives are effectively implemented and sustained. Digitally mature organisations can respond more effectively to market changes, regulatory requirements, and technological advancements.

Table 7. Digital maturity profile example for the digital twin use case for SH5.

% Score	Maturity Levels	Maturity Assessment Examples
0-20	Unaware	Manual inspections; SCADA used only for alarms
20-40	Conceptual	Leadership aware of digital twin concept but no digital roadmap; Basic SCADA data collected but not integrated
40-60	Defined	Data from sensors partially integrated to dashboards; Stand-alone turbine or component-level simulation models exist
60-80	Integrated	Centralised data platform integrating SCADA, Weather forecasts, vibration data and Structural health monitoring; Predictive maintenance capability implemented.
80-100	Transformed	Turbines self-optimise based on wind conditions; Autonomous Anomaly Detection.

2.3 Suggestions for team leaders

SL1. Empower teams with true ownership for digital transformation

Why this is important: The IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey results showed that teams, rather than entire organisations, are the primary engines of digitalisation culture in the wind energy sector. Empowering teams with ownership over digital initiatives fosters agility, innovation, and accountability. Whilst bottom-up approaches still need to be supported by management top-down, it can enable bottom-up momentum, which is especially critical in organisations where top-down strategies are slow or fragmented. When teams have the autonomy to experiment and the resources to act, they are more likely to adopt digital tools, share knowledge, and drive meaningful transformation.

How it could be implemented: Team leaders should provide their teams with clear digital goals, decision-making authority, and accountability for resource use. They can introduce “Digital Pioneers” within their teams, who are individuals or subgroups with an annual experimentation budget, access to digital tools, and protected time for piloting new ideas. These pioneers can lead internal demos, participate in cross-team learning sessions, and showcase results in innovation town-halls. They act as catalysts for experimentation, innovation, and adoption of digital tools and practices. Making success stories visible across the organisation can inspire others and reinforce a culture of ownership and experimentation. An example of how the Digital Pioneer could interact with team members, the team leader and the CDO (see SM4) is shown in Figure 6. This figure also shows an example of how team-level ownership and the Digital Pioneer model described in SL1 could underpin the distribution of generic responsibilities summarised in Table 8, which can also be linked to broader ESG governance and relevant SDG contributions. The reader is referred to [8] for a discussion of different digital roles.

Figure 6. Example of the role of team members and Digital Pioneer in wind energy digitalisation.

For clarity, the Digital Pioneers operate at the team level as early adopters and experimenters (as shown in Figure 6), while Digital Ambassadors are introduced under SM4 operators at the organisational level to ensure visibility, cross-team learning and alignment with the CDO’s digital strategy (see Figure 3). These roles complement rather than replace each other.

Table 8: Example of different “owners” for different wind energy digital activities.

Digital activity	Role description	Owner
Asset health monitoring model development	Develop predictive maintenance and fault detection models	Wind data analyst
Data preparation	Ensure data accuracy and completeness	Wind data manager
SCADA & sensor data integration	Integrate SCADA and environmental data	Wind data engineer
KPI tracking	Measure business value and benefits of digital initiatives (uptime, cost savings, ESG metrics)	CDO
Cybersecurity and compliance implementation	Implement secure data-sharing protocols and ensure compliance with industry standards	IT security specialist
Innovation demonstration and peer learning implementation	Organise “Show-and-Share” sessions and fail-forward workshops to promote transparency	Digital Pioneer

SL2. Make team success stories visible and integrate them into strategic communications

Why this is important: The IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey results highlight that teams are the strongest engines of digitalisation culture in the wind energy sector. When team-level innovation and experimentation are made visible, it reinforces a bottom-up momentum for transformation. Sharing success stories builds trust, encourages cross-team learning, and helps overcome resistance to change. It also aligns with the broader goal of fostering a culture of openness, collaboration, and continuous improvement.

How it could be implemented: Team leaders could establish peer-learning formats such as “Show and Fail” sessions, where teams present both successful and unsuccessful digital experiments, and internal demo days to showcase tools, workflows, and lessons learned. These formats promote transparency and normalise learning from failure. Success stories should be documented and featured in newsletters, dashboards, and leadership briefings. Teams could be recognised through awards or storytelling segments during annual “Digital Culture Rituals”, helping embed their achievements into the organisation’s strategic narrative. To foster a culture of learning, visibility, and strategic alignment, teams should be encouraged to document and share their digitalisation efforts. Using a standard template, stories should be submitted quarterly and reviewed for inclusion in strategic communications. This practice not only celebrates innovation but also promotes cross-team learning and reinforces the organisation’s commitment to digital transformation. An example of different “Digital Culture Rituals” is given in Table 9, along with a suggestion of how this could make team success stories visible.

Table 9: Examples of different “Digital Culture Rituals”.

“Digital Culture Ritual” (internal)	How it makes team success stories visible
Internal innovation sprint	Teams build something in a short sprint and demo outcomes; results are documented as “what got built” stories
Large-scale hackathons	Bring together different teams for (collaborative) hackathons to discuss ideas and to design/develop digital applications. Report the results in terms of prototypes and “employee-built impact” stories
AI or digital innovation days / events	Report on the practical benefits across business units
Weekly “Show and Tell” sessions	Other business units become aware of work-in-progress and outcomes
Leadership “Show and Tell” sessions	Other business units become aware of work-in-progress and outcomes
Digital Experience Day run by digital champions of Digital Pioneer	A dedicated event where employees experience in-house digitisation projects and future tech firsthand

SL3. Apply proven team practices to improve leadership capability and cross-team decision-making

Why this is important: Strong leadership and effective cross-team collaboration are essential for scaling digital transformation across complex organisations. The IEA Wind Task 43 Culture Survey results highlight that teams are often more agile and culturally prepared for digitalisation than their parent organisations. By applying proven team practices, meaning practices that have been traditionally used for team leadership before digitalisation became important, organisations can bridge gaps between units, foster shared ownership, and build leadership capacity that supports experimentation, transparency, and innovation.

How it could be implemented: Team leads could run regular “show-and-tell” demonstrations of team workflows to promote visibility and mutual learning. Teams can compile an internal digital playbook in a shared knowledge base to document tools, processes, and lessons learned. Rotating “digital champions” between teams can help cross-pollinate ideas, build empathy, and strengthen leadership networks. These practices encourage openness, reduce silos, and create a feedback-rich environment where leadership is distributed and adaptive. An example of applying proven team practices to improve leadership capability and cross-team decision-making is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Example of applying proven team practices to improve leadership capability and cross-team decision-making.

Section	Details
Context	A global wind energy company faced challenges in scaling digital transformation due to siloed decision-making and inconsistent leadership practices.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rotating Digital Champions between O&M and engineering teams. ● Monthly show-and-tell sessions for workflow visibility. ● Developed a digital playbook documenting tools and lessons learned. ● Embedded transformational leadership principles (vision, empowerment, feedback) into leadership training.
Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased cross-team collaboration by 40%. ● Reduced duplication of digital initiatives by 25%. ● Leadership capability scores improved by 30% in internal surveys
Visibility Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Share success stories in leadership briefings. ● Recognised top-performing teams during annual “Digital Culture Awards.” ● Shared results in an industry webinar hosted by IEA Wind Task 43.
ESG & SDG Impact	SDG 8: Decent Work & Economic Growth SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure – Strengthened innovation culture. SDG 17: Partnerships for Goals – Fostered collaboration across teams and external partners.

3. Conclusions

In this document, concrete suggestions with examples have been made to guide different stakeholder groups (central management, HR departments and team leaders) towards fostering digitalisation in their organisation through digital organisational cultures. Where applicable, implementation suggestions were made for one use case, in which we imagine a team within an organisation to be developing and operating a digital twin for wind farm health monitoring. The suggestions are summarised below. The division between stakeholders and suggestions is not entirely strict, and stakeholders may overlap in some cases, depending on the organisation's structure.

For central management:

- SM1. Publish a clear, multi-year digitalisation roadmap with goals, owners and milestones
- SM2. Make digital transformation a required goal in every business unit
- SM3. Create a centralised support hub with digitalisation expertise, decision-making capacity, and agile budget access to actively enable team-initiated digital ideas
- SM4. Appoint a Chief Digital Officer and “digital ambassadors”
- SM5. Flatten decision layers, and normalise constructive feedback and continuous learning
- SM6. Institutionalise experimentation and blameless learning at the organisational level

For HR departments:

- SH1. Provide digitalisation training
- SH2. Recruit domain-aware digitalisation experts
- RH3. Train leaders to champion digitalisation
- SH4. Design hybrid learning formats that combine digital skills training with emotional readiness
- SH5. Create a “digitalisation maturity profile” per unit

For team leaders:

- SL1. Empower teams with true ownership for digital transformation
- SL2. Make team success stories visible and integrate them into strategic communications
- SL3. Apply proven team practices to improve leadership capability and cross-team decision-making

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